

EVALUATION OF INDIGENOUS BOTANICALS AGAINST RED RUST FLOUR BEETLE, *TRIBOLIUM CASTANEUM* (HERBST.) IN STORED SESAMER. Sheeba Jasmine^{1*}, C. Raja Babu², K. Kavitha³ and V. Karunakaran⁴¹ICAR- Krishi Vigyan Kendra (TNAU), Sirugamani, Trichy- 639115, Tamil Nadu, India.²ICAR- Krishi Vigyan Kendra (TNAU), Sirugamani, Trichy -639115, Tamil Nadu, India.³ICAR- Krishi Vigyan Kendra (TNAU), Thirupatisaram, Kanyakumari- 629901, Tamil Nadu,⁴ICAR- Krishi Vigyan Kendra (TNAU), Needamangalam, Thiruvavur - 614 404,

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Abstract

Sesame Sesamum indicum Linn. is the most indigenous oilseed crop and described as the “Queen of Oil Crop” of the world as well as one of the major oil seed crops of India. Sesame crop is attacked by 29 species of insect pests in different stages of its plant growth. The red rust flour beetle, *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) is an important pest of stored sesame. In order to find the effect of various botanicals against red rust flour beetle, laboratory experiments were undertaken at Regional Research Station, Vriddhachalam during 2018-20 comprising seven treatments in four replications with VRI-2 sesame variety. The treatments viz., turmeric powder, citrus peel powder, citrus leaf powder, curry leaf powder, NSK powder, neem leaf powder @ 5g/kg seed each and untreated check. Observation on mortality of beetles was recorded after 24 hours and 5, 10, 15, 20 and 25 days after release. Simultaneously germination test was conducted and pooled mortality was worked out. The results expressed that the seeds treated with NSK powder @ 5 g/kg registered maximum mortality (6.00 %) of *Tribolium* beetles within 24 hours after release and 42.25 per cent mortality on 15 days after release (DAR), it was followed by neem leaf powder @ 5g/kg (33.25%) and curry leaf powder @ 5g/kg (31.25%), respectively on 15 DAR. Sesame seed treated with neem seed kernel powder @ 5g/kg registered highest pooled mortality of 68.25 per cent followed by neem leaf powder (61.25%) on 25 DAR. The per cent mean seed germination was high in sesame treated with curry leaf powder@ 5g/kg (96.50%) followed by neem seed kernel powder @ 5g/kg (96.00) and untreated check (95.25%).

Key words: Sesame, *Tribolium castaneum*, botanicals, efficacy

Introduction

Sesame *Sesamum indicum* L., the ancient oil seed crop of India, is grown from time immemorial. Nine edible oilseeds are cultivated in India and sesame ranks fifth in production, following groundnut, rapeseed, soybean and sunflower. India contributes 30 per cent of world's sesame production. One of the major constraints in sesame production is the damage caused by insect pests. Sesame seed contains 46-64 per cent oil, 20-25 per cent protein, 14-20 per cent carbohydrates and minerals (5-7%). Totally, ninety six per cent fatty acids viz., oleic (43%), linoleic (35%), palmitic (11%) and stearic acids (7%) are present in sesame. Moreover, Vitamins E, A, B, Niacin and minerals like calcium, phosphorus, iron, copper, magnesium, zinc and potassium are present. Sesame oil contains 4.5-5 g excess protein compared to other oilseed crops, which is equal to egg protein.

Among the various insect pests of sesame, red rust flour beetle, *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) is an important pest of stored seeds of sesame. It causes 8.5-22.3 per cent losses. Chemical means of pest control involves environmental pollution as well as high cost. Hence developing low cost effective pest management strategy involving botanicals facilitate to achieve minimum loss in stored sesame and quality as well as monetary benefits to farmers and bring out green environment. In order to find the effect of various botanicals to red rust flour beetle, investigations were undertaken during 2018-20 at Regional Research Station (RRS), Vriddhachalam.

Materials And Methods

Three laboratory experiments were conducted with VRI-2 sesame variety under Completely Randomized Block Design comprising seven treatments in four replications. The treatments evaluated were turmeric powder, citrus peel powder, citrus leaf powder, curry leaf powder, NSK powder, neem leaf powder @ 5g/kg seed each and untreated check. Sesame seeds were well dried and cleaned (< 8% moisture content). Various parts of botanicals like rhizome, leaves, peel and seeds were collected, well dried and powdered and sieved. The nucleus culture of *Tribolium* was obtained from Farm stores, RRS, Vriddhachalam. Beetles were mass multiplied in sesame seeds. Five hundred grams of sesame seeds were taken and treated with each botanicals, well mixed, placed aside. The experiment was conducted under laboratory condition (28 ±2°C and 80 ± 5% RH). After twenty four hours of treatment, ten grams of seeds were taken from the lot (500 g) for each replication, placed inside the jars and twenty beetles were released. Observation on mortality of beetles was recorded after 24 hours and 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 days after release.

$$\text{Per cent mortality} = \frac{\text{Dead insects}}{\text{Total insects released}} \times 100$$

Simultaneously four hundred seeds of sesame drawn separately (hundred seed/replicate) to test the germination. Pooled mortality was worked out. The data obtained were analysed statistically following OP STAT (Sheoran *et al.*, 1998)

Results And Discussion

Pooled mean mortality revealed that the seeds treated with NSK powder @ 5 g/kg seed registered the maximum mortality (6.00 %) of *Tribolium* beetles within 24 hours after release followed by neem leaf powder @ 5g/kg, curry leaf powder@ 5g/kg and citrus peel powder@ 5g/kg, respectively (4.38, 4.00 and 3.63 %). On 25 DAR, NSK powder @ 5 g/kg seed registered the highest mortality (70.25%). Neem leaf powder @ 5 g/kg registered 63.67 percent on 25 DAR followed by curry leaf powder (57.00%) and citrus peel powder (55.00%) (Table 1). Further, seed germination was higher in NSK powder (95.25%) followed by curry leaf powder (95.13%) and neem leaf powder (93.63%), respectively. In Toto, NSK powder and neem leaf powder were found to be performed better.

Present findings were in accordance with Patil *et al.*, (2015) who reported that highest per cent mortality of *T. castaneum* was recorded in neem seed powder @ 5 g/100 g (89.25%). The next best treatments were neem leaf powder @ 5 g/100 g and neem seed powder @ 3 g/100 g which recorded 86.98 and 85.98 per cent mortality. Mamun *et al.* (2009) also found that, neem seed extract showed highest toxic effect (52.50 % mortality). Hameed *et al.* (2012) showed that neem leaves extract recorded highest mortality (45%) at (2.5 % conc.) at 168 hrs exposure than kanair leaves extract by using filter paper dip method in stored wheat grain. Whereas, Iram *et al.* (2013) reported that, ethanol extract of *Citrus reticulata* (L.) peel @ 2 ml was found to be the strongest repellent with 70.66 per cent repellency and ethanol extract of *C. reticulata* leaves @ 2 ml was the most effective (97.66 %) at 21st day of exposure against *T. castaneum*, respectively. Ali *et al.* (2001) reported that the fumigation of *Eucalyptus* sp and *Cinnamomum verum* oils mixed methyl alcohol resulted in high mortality rates of 60.67 and 63.33%, respectively. Application of neem seed kernel powder @ 5g/kg is effective against *T. castaneum* in stored sesame followed by neem leaf powder @ 5g/kg for protecting the sesame seeds. Rests of botanicals were found to provide optimal protection against *T.*

castaneum. Hence, seed treatment with NSK powder @ 5g/kg seed would be more appropriate for successful management of red rust flour beetle in stored sesame.

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Table.1 Management of red rust flour beetle, *Tribolium castaneum* in stored sesame

Tr. No.	Treatments	Germination (%)	Pooled Mortality (%)*					
			24 hours	5 DAT	10 DAT	15 DAT	20 DAT	25 DAT
T1	Turmeric powder @ 5 g/kg seed	91.75 (73.97)	3.12 (10.32)	11.00 (19.06)	18.75 (25.67)	26.00 (30.61)	36.25 (36.51)	50.63 (45.39)
T2	Citrus Peel powder @ 5 g/kg seed	90.25 (71.47)	3.63 (10.82)	12.50 (19.67)	20.50 (26.94)	27.50 (31.59)	38.50 (38.03)	55.00 (47.87)
T3	Citrus leaf powder @ 5 g/kg seed	90.00 (71.18)	2.50 (7.25)	12.75 (19.94)	14.75 (21.85)	23.75 (28.96)	38.75 (38.47)	52.00 (46.20)
T4	Curry leaf powder @ 5 g/kg seed	95.13 (77.33)	4.38 (12.04)	16.25 (23.63)	21.88 (27.91)	31.25 (33.98)	41.75 (39.83)	57.00 (49.11)
T5	NSK powder @ 5 g/kg seed	95.25 (77.72)	6.00 (14.13)	15.25 (22.97)	28.88 (32.48)	48.25 (44.52)	57.00 (47.78)	70.25 (57.16)
T6	Neem leaf powder @ 5 g/kg seed	93.63 (75.92)	4.00 (11.53)	16.38 (23.74)	24.13 (29.43)	37.50 (37.20)	44.25 (41.69)	63.67 (52.68)
T7	Untreated check	92.25 (74.53)	0.00 (0.47)	1.88 (5.72)	5.50 (12.95)	12.75 (19.94)	18.50 (25.11)	28.50 (31.83)
	SEm		0.74	1.47	1.75	1.84	1.86	2.00
	CD(p=0.05)		2.50	3.32	3.81	4.05	4.08	4.46
	CV (%)		7.47	4.88	4.40	4.33	4.01	4.23

*Figures within parentheses are arcsine transformed